

**A STUDY ON GROWTH AND IMPACTS OF INDIA'S FOREIGN TRADE -
AN ENGINE FOR ENTREPRENEURSHIP AND ECONOMIC
DEVELOPMENT
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Abstract. This study main investigates that the growth of Exports, Imports and Trade Balance from 1949-50 to 2018-19 in India. It also reveals that the India's export profile state wise share for 2016-17 to 2018-19. This study furthers study on India performance in global trade 2011-2017 and finally examines that the India's exports and imports by destination for 8 digits HS code level 2016-17 to 2018-19. This present research data were processed with help of descriptive statistical and inferential statistical techniques applied such as correlation, regression, ANOVA and Paired t test were tested for various hypotheses. India's exports by destination 2016-17 to 2018-19 revealed that the first position secured by USA, followed by United Arab Emirates and third rank secured by China. Imports by destination 2016-17 to 2018-19 revealed that the first position secured by China, followed by USA and third rank secured by United Arab Emirates. Top ten exports destinations were secured by during the years 2016-17 (50.83%), 2017-18 (50.78%) and 2018-19 (50.78%). Top ten destinations imports were secured by during the years 2016-17 (50.82%), 2017-18 (50.32%) and 2018-19 (52.86%). This investigation concluded that the India has passed and amendment successfully different most important commercial, legal and economic reforms in the past two decades. It shows constructive impact on improving the business environment for international trade into India it will be golden opportunity for strengthening positive trade balance position of India in future.

Key Words: Imports, Exports, Globalization, Balance of trade, Business, India, Regions

1. Introduction

Global trade is the exchange of merchandise of goods and services across the countries in the all over the world. It is the most customary form of global business form and has played a most important role in determining world foreign trade, globalization, privatization, liberalization, exports, import, trade balance and balance payment position of world history (Belay Seyoum 2009). International trade is an increasingly (Friederike Niepmann 2014) acknowledged practice of the 21st century (Jim Sherlock et al, 2008) for global exchange of goods and services for fulfilling needs and wants of all nations and its people for especially scarcity of natural resources, manpower and other services. During the end beginning of 19th century industrialization, the technological innovations growing of giving origin of numerous new industries in manufacturing, construction, banking and insurance, healthcare services, food processing, electronic goods, computers, civil aviation, petroleum and its allied products are likely to have positive impact.

E-commerce, E-banking, Online services markings, Online and digital trades are in the modern days offering new avenues to entrepreneurs and small and medium enterprise around the world (Azevedo 2017). It is engage in creative and driving force for economic growth (Guterres 2018), direct and indirect employment generation (veeramani C. et al 2016), income generation and best return of investment for around the world (Robetro

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Azevedo 2018). Globalization and liberalization of international trade (Bhat T P et al 2006) are deciding factors for nation building and sustainable development (Roman Mogilivskii 2012). The increasing dimensions of foreign trade will bring into lowering of tariff barriers for (UNCTAD 2013) supportive of developing and underdeveloped countries growth (Konstantin M. Wacker et al, 2014).

Economists, Nobel laureates, policy makers, governments and researchers all over the world have realized the potential of global trade (Xia Jing 2013) have been speedy growth of many energetic rising economics (Rahul Khullar 2011) & (Jagjeet Lally 2009). Policy makers countenance the various challenges of strengthening existing policies (Tanu M Goyal et al 2017) and formulating new trade policies (Sandra Polaksi et al, 2018). The growth of Indian international trade would create that the universal model of economic revolutions (Rahul Anand et al, 2015), for resource to transferred across the all over countries of the world to get better profitable performance (Jaratin Lily et al 2014). The export, import and foreign trade policies of a country must be international standards (Obaid Ur Rehman 2015) to facilitate foreign trade diversification (Prasad et al, 2017) and development of new markets (Parthapratim Pal 2013).

Internationally exports, imports of goods and services registered growth (Prasad H.A.C 2012) in the recent years for the impacts of globalization (Urata, S et al 2017), foreign direct investment (FDI), Special Economic Zones (SEZ) and multinational companies are changing global environment will create new avenues of demand and opportunities (Niels Utoft Andersen et al, 2017) for India. Recently central, state governments, national and international organizations, export promoting agencies should be focused national priority for export sectors are most important and greater involvement in while structuring and put into operation of export policy (Prasad H.A.C 2012).

This is normally happening in developing nations to have huge amount of deficit in balance of trade position in initial stages for imports of capital goods (Inkyo Cheong et al 2015). Before and after liberalization phases (Pual J et al, 2007) offered enormousness opportunities for trading (Betina Dimaranan et al, 2007) of free flow of global trade (Sudip Ranjan Basu 2012) for considerable amount of economic growth (Dilyara I. et al 217) & (Peng sun 2010). This shows that in international trade and services (Arpita Mukherjee et al, 2017) during 2016 8th position secured in major exporter at the same time 10th position in major importer of services (WTO, 2017).

International trade contributed significantly amount of foreign reserves in the latter part of 19th century (Bhat T P 2011) and also positive stable growth in exports after the 1991 economic reforms (PHD Research Bureau 2015) of India. Exports and imports are useful role (Musibau Adetunji Babatunde 2014) in integrating (Gholamreza Fathipour et al, 2014) numerous economics of the world (Priyanka Sahni 2014) and it improves in real GDP (Livio Stracca 2013) and deciding factor of country trade of balance.

1.1 Importance and significance of the study

International trade has phenomenal growth across the world after the origin of various international agencies like World Trade Organization, World Bank, and International Monetary Fund and liberalization of trade barriers for the various nations (Subhash Jagdambe 2016). Before 1991, India was a closed economy (Michele Alessandrini 2009).

Liberalization of international trade and necessary new economic reforms has been implemented successfully in India since 1991 (Smitha Francis 2015). In order to facilitate foreign trade, Government of India, Ministry of finance, DIPP, Ministry of commerce and trade, and Ministry of corporate affairs, DFGT consults with various Export Promotion Councils (EPCs) and various participants of international trade from time to time (Foreign Trade Policy 2015-20) introduced various new policies reforms (Mahesh Sharma et al, 2015) like subsidies for exports, duty free and tax holiday.

India post economic reform stage (Upender M 2007) exports are growing (Matthieu Bussiere et al, 2018) it is reflected in positive position in balance of payment, foreign exchange of income, employment (Ruba Abu Shihab et al, 2014) and share of world exports growing steadily (Mehdi Raissi et al, 2015). India's simple trade policies (Michele Ruta 2012) results into foreign trade expansion (Afafa Abdul et al, 2015) and economic development (Kunalsen 2008). Foreign trade provides mutual benefits (Sunanda Sen 2010) for both notions involved in outflows of goods and services for one country to another country. The outcome of this movement creates inwards and outwards foreign exchange into two nations (Pushpalata Singh 2012). It is prominent factor (Sen Gupta A.K et al 2013) in the positive balance of trade position for especially developing nations.

International trade has multiplier effects (Velnampy T et al 2013) which is useful national economic model construction. This is considered as engine (Sayef Bakari et al, 2017) for economic and national development. Post liberalization phase (Chandrima Sikdar et al, 2011) India had massive growth in Indian exports (Ranajit Chakrabarty et al, 2012) bring into high volume of foreign exchange reserves (Doekate Tai Balasahenb 2013) and encouraging overall economic growth of the country. In these circumstances this study focused on import, export and trade balance of India during years 1949-50 to 2018-19.

1.2. Review of literature

Ramesh C. Paudel (2014) concluded that the improving export performance is main objectives of developing countries by way of liberalizations reforms. Michele Ruta (2012), found that the various factors added to expansion of trade, industrialization, taxes, cost of production, selling and distribution cost for international trade growth. Anjani Kumar (2010), results showed that the economic liberalization and policy reforms are key for universal market opportunities. Purva Yadav (2012), suggested that the economic reforms and political environments during past decades contributed a fair amount of global market place. Rajesh K Pillanina (2008), found that the India international trade highly improved during last decade. Michael F. Martin et al (2014), found that the India business situations has a positive changes in the past decades.

Shubhada Sabade (2014), found that the various factors affecting balance of payment failure and foreign exchange reserve position of India. Suresh D. Tendulkar (2000), results showed that the global trading option help as an influential factor for high rate of economic growth. Pravakar Shaoo et al (2009) studied that India's wide ranges of economic policies reforms and found that steady economic growth in the last decades. Nagesh Kumer (2001), results showed that the foreign trade to GDP rising positively fourteen percent in 1980 and around twenty percent during 1990. Nalini Rajan Kumaret al (2005) suggested that the increasing foreign trade demand by way of reducing cost of production goods and services. (Manoj Kumar Sinha 2016) concluded that the economic reforms have influenced

exceptional growth of Indian economy. Aurjun kifle (2017) found that the foreign trade created employment and increases foreign exchange earnings. Murat Seker (2011), results indicated that the various Asian nations had sustained high export growth.

1.2.1. Research Gap

This research studied that the many articles, journals, books, discussion papers, working papers, policy notes, and thesis, dissertations, projects reports, newspapers, magazine, seminars, conferences, workshop edited volumes relating to export, import, trade balance, balance of payment, foreign trade and international trade at national and international publications. In this position this mainly focuses on import, export and trade balance of India during years 1949-50 to 2018-19. It will be helpful for frame research design, research questions and find out research gap of this study. Outcome of after analyzing showed that there is limited number of research was carry out in the past. This current study is to be conduct taking into consideration of various recent Indian corporate sectors, taxation and economic reforms. In this way this current study different form the past studies in many approaches and contributes some amount the results to existing literature.

1.2.2. Methods of Data Collection

This current research study data collected secondary source of data from ministry of commerce and trade, Directorate General of Commercial Intelligence & Statistics (DGCI&S), Kolkata, monthly bulletin on foreign trade statistics, Monthly MIS report on export promotion schemes, India budget documents, and economic survey reports, Government of India publications, Directorate General of Foreign Trade (DGFT), various ministries annual reports and websites publications, World Trade Organization (WTO), Reserve bank of India and other publication relating current study.

1.2.3. Statistical Techniques and Research methodology Applied.

This present research data were processed with help of descriptive statistical techniques applied such as tables, charts, mean, standard deviation and averages. It is used to find out descriptive outcome of data. It also examine with help inferential statistical techniques applied such as correlation, regression, ANOVA and Paired t test were tested for various hypotheses. The present research study period data of exports, import and balance of trade were starting from 1949-50 to 2018-19.

1.2.4. The main objectives research of the study

These objectives are as follows: 1) To examine the growth of India exports, imports and trade balance from 1949-50 to 2018-19. 2) To examine the principal commodities of India exports and imports from 1949-50 to 2018-19. 3) To study on top ten exports and imports by country and state wise share form 2016-17 to 2018-19. 4) To study on India performance in global trade from 2011-2017.

Besides we include a reference to the relationships between foreign trade and industrial development in India. As seen in Guisan (2004) industrial production per capita has usually a positive impact on exports per capita, and the increase of exports contribute to increase the capacity of the country to import intermediate goods useful for economic development. That study presents the estimation of econometric models of India, China, Japan and a pool of these three countries for the period 1960-2002 and concludes: "*Industrial development of China, India and other Asian countries, following the example of Japan and other developed countries, has been one of the most important economic events of the last*

decades of the 20th century. Challenges for India and China during the first decades of the 21st century are formidable, and both countries will achieve a high rate of sustainable economic development if their policies are focused on improving the educational level of population, industrial development, and trade, among other factors. The econometric models here presented show some of the main positive direct and indirect effects of industry and foreign trade on economic growth, as well as the high positive impact of education on economic development...".

In Guisan, Aguayo and Exposito (2014) we may notice a positive evolution of real value-added of manufacturing per capita in India for the period 2000-2010 and its positive impact on economic development.

2. Descriptive data analysis results discussion

2.1 India trade performance in the international trade (2011-2017)

The above table 1 shows that the export and import performance in percentage share of India in the world trade and India's rank in world trade (calendar year wise) from 2011 to 2017. India's share in world merchandise plus services exports in percentages starting with 2011 (1.94%) ending with 2017 (2.10%). India's share in world merchandise plus services imports in percentages starting with 2011(2.60%) ending with 2017(2.60%).

Table 1 India Performance in International Trade(2011-2017)			
Performance of India exports percentage share in international trade. India's Share			
	Merchandise exports	Commercial services exports	Merchandise plus services exports
2011	1.65	3.18	1.94
2012	1.6	3.25	1.92
2013	1.66	3.12	1.95
2014	1.7	3.06	1.99
2015	1.62	3.2	1.98
2016	1.65	3.3	2.30
2017	1.68	3.47	2.10
Performance of India imports percentage of share in international trade. India's Share			
	Merchandise imports	Commercial services imports	Merchandise plus services imports
2011	2.51	2.99	2.60
2012	2.62	2.97	2.68
2013	2.45	2.73	2.50
2014	2.42	2.55	2.45
2015	2.25	2.59	2.32
2016	2.13	2.78	2.27
2017	2.48	3.02	2.60

India's rank in international trade				
Years	Merchandise exports	Merchandise imports	Services imports	Services imports
2011	19	7	7	9
2012	19	7	7	10
2013	20	7	7	10
2014	19	8	8	11
2015	21	8	8	11
2016	21	8	8	11
2017	20	8	8	10

Source: Monthly bulletin on foreign trade July 2019

2.2 India's Export, Imports and trade Balance (Rs. In Crores) 1949-50 to 2018-19

The following table 2 clearly exhibited that the India's exports, imports and trade balance (Rs. In Crores) 1949-50 to 2018-19 totally 70 years were presented. During year 1949-50 showed that exports (including re-exports) in 485 (Crore), in case of imports showed in 617 (Crore) and trade balance showed in 132 (Crore). Ending with year 2018-19 demonstrated that exports (including re-exports) in 2307663 (Crore), in case of imports exhibited in 3594373 (Crore) and trade balance showed at (-1286710) (Crore). Out of 70 years only 2 had positive trade balance.

2.3 Export, Imports and trade balance of India 1949-50 to 2018-19

Table 2, in the Annex, clearly exhibited that the exports, imports and trade balance of India (US\$ Million) 1949-50 to 2018-19 totally 70 years were presented. During year 1949-50 showed that exports (including re-exports) in 1016 (US\$ Million), in case of imports showed in 1292 (US\$ Million) and trade balance showed in -276 (US\$ Million). Ending with year 2018-19 demonstrated that exports (including re-exports) in 329536 (US\$ Million), in case of imports exhibited in 514034 (US\$ Million) and trade balance showed at (-184498) (US\$ Million).

2.4 Principal of exports during 1949-50 to 2018-19

The above table 4 and 5 shows that principal of exports (Value in Rs. in Crore) during 1949-50 to 2018-19. Agricultural & allied products results shows that starting with 1960-61 (284 Crore) and (596 US\$ Million) ending with 2018-19 (271358 Crore) and (38829 US\$ Million). Ores and minerals results shows that starting with 1960-61 (52 Crore) and (109 US\$ Million) ending with 2018-19 (41446 Crore) and (5927 US\$ Million). Manufactured goods results shows that starting with 1960-61 (291 Crore) and (610 US\$ Million) ending with 2018-19 (1621779 Crore) and (231953 US\$ Million). Minerals fuels and lubricants shows that starting with 1960-61 (7 Crore) and (15 US\$ Million) ending with 2018-19 (335148 Crore) and (47874 US\$ Million). Total Exports shows that starting with 1960-61 (642 Crore) and (1346 US\$ Million) ending with 2018-19 (2307663 Crore) and (330070 US\$ Million).

2.5 Principal of imports during 1949-50 to 2018-19

The above table 6 and 7 shows that principal of imports (Value in Rs. in Crore) during 1949-50 to 2018-19. Total imports shows that starting with 1960-61 (1122 Crore) ending with (3594373 Crore) in the year 2018-19. Total imports shows that starting with 1960-61 (2353 US\$ Million) ending with (514034 US\$ Million) in the year 2018-19.

2.6 India's export performance by destination

Table 8 shows that the India's export performance by destination 2016-17 to 2018-19. The first position secured by USA during the years 2016-17 (42212.27) (US\$ Million), 2017-18(47878.48)(US\$ Million) and2018-19(47432.83)(US\$ Million).

In the next position secured United Arab Emiratesduring the years 2016-17 (42212.27) (US\$ Million), 2017-18(47878.48)(US\$ Million) and 2018-19(47432.83)(US\$ Million). Third rank secured by China during the years 2016-17 (42212.27) (US\$ Million), 2017-18(47878.48)(US\$ Million) and 2018-19(47432.83)(US\$ Million).

Share of India's top ten countries exports destinations secured by during the years 2016-17 (140226.6) (US\$ Million) (50.83%), 2017-18 (154118.5)(US\$ Million) (50.78%) and 2018-19 (150696.9)(US\$ Million) (50.78%).

Remaining destinations during the year contributed by during the years 2016-17 (135625.9) (US\$ Million) (49.17%), 2017-18 (149407.6)(US\$ Million) (49.22%) and 2018-19(178780.23)(US\$ Million) (49.22%).

Table 8 Performance of India's exports by destination						
S No	Country	(Value in US\$ Million)			% Change	
		2016-17	2017-18	2018-19	2016-17/ 2017-18	2017-18/ 2018-19
1	USA	42212.27	47878.48	47432.83	13.42	9.54
2	U Arab Emts	31175.5	28146.12	27290.47	-9.72	5.8
3	China P Rp	10171.89	13333.53	1506674	31.08	28.35
4	Hong Kong	14047.24	14690.27	11981.03	4.58	-12.63
5	Singapore	9564.58	10202.82	9495.99	6.67	1.44
6	UK	8530.07	9691.07	8391.97	13.61	-4.7
7	Bangladesh Pr	6820.11	8614.35	8080	26.31	5.3
8	Germany	7181.61	8687.8	8060.74	20.97	3.08
9	Netherland	5069.69	6261.14	7919.57	23.5	41.4
10	Nepal	5453.59	6612.96	6977.55	21.36	17.47
Top 10 destinations		140226.6	154118.5	150696.9	9.01	-2.27
% Share India's top 10 export destinations		50.83	50.78	50.78		
Total of rest of the above		135625.9	149407.6	178780.23	10.16	19.66
% Share of rest of destinations exports		49.17	49.22	49.22		
Total Export		275852.4	303526.2	329477.13	10.03	8.55
Source: Monthly Bulletin on Foreign Trade May 2019						

2.7 Performance of India's Imports by origin

Table 9 shows that the India's export performance by destination 2016-17 to 2018-19.

The first position secured by China during the years 2016-17 (61283.03) (US\$ Million), 2017-18(76380.70)(US\$ Million) and2018-19(70318.03)(US\$ Million).

In the next position secured USA during the years 2016-17 (22307.44) (US\$ Million), 2017-18(26611.03)(US\$ Million) and 2018-19(35434.33)(US\$ Million).

Third rank secured by United Arab Emirates during the years 2016-17 (21509.83) (US\$ Million), 2017-18(21739.11)(US\$ Million) and 2018-19(29765.70)(US\$ Million).

Top ten Imports origins of India's secured by during the years 2016-17 (195333.41) (US\$ Million) (50.82%), 2017-18 (234282.9)(US\$ Million) (50.32%) and 2018-19 (271317.8)(US\$ Million) (52.86%).

Rest of the imports were secured by during the years 2016-17 (189023.62) (US\$ Million) (49.18%), 2017-18 (231298.1)(US\$ Million) (49.68%) and 2018-19(242004.6)(US\$ Million) (47.14%).

Table 9 Performance of India's Imports by origin						
S.No	Origin	(Value in US\$ Million)			% Change	
		2016-17	2017-18	2018-19	2016-17/ 2017-18	2017-18/ 2018-19
1	China P Rp	61283.03	76380.70	70318.03	24.64	-7.94
2	USA	22307.44	26611.03	35434.33	19.29	33.16
3	U Arab Emts	21509.83	21739.11	29765.70	1.07	36.92
4	Saudi Arab	19972.40	22069.66	28479.21	10.50	29.04
5	Iraq	11707.94	17615.81	22372.47	50.46	27
6	Switzerland	17248.68	18923.05	18076.88	9.71	-4.47
7	Hong Kong	8204.18	10675.98	17986.95	30.13	68.48
8	Korea Rp	12585.35	16361.77	16758.76	30.01	2.43
9	Singapore	7086.57	7466.99	16281.58	5.37	118.05
10	Indonesia	13427.99	16438.80	15843.93	22.42	-3.62
Total of above		195333.41	234282.9	271317.8	19.94	15.81
% Share India's top 10 Import destinations		50.82	50.32	52.86		
Total of rest of the above		189023.62	231298.1	242004.6	22.36	4.63
% Share of rest of destinations imports		49.18	49.68	47.14		
Total imports		384357.03	465581	513322.4	21.13	10.25
Source: Monthly Bulletin on Foreign Trade May 2019						

3. Major findings of the study

1. Share of merchandise exports of India in world shows that during the year 2011 starting with (1.65%) and ending with 2017 (1.68%).
2. It also indicated that the share of commercial services exports of India in world during the year 2011 starting with (3.18%) and ending with 2017 (3.47%).
3. It also indicated that the merchandise plus services exports share of India in world during the year 2011 starting with (1.94%) and ending with 2017 (2.10%).
4. Share of merchandise imports of India in world shows that during the year 2011 starting with (2.51%) and ending with 2017 (2.48%).
5. It also designated that the India's share in world commercial services imports that during the year 2011 starting with (2.99%) and ending with 2017 (3.09%).
6. It also revealed that the share of merchandise plus services imports of India in world during the year 2011 starting with (2.10%) and ending with 2017 (2.10%).
7. India's rank in world trade (calendar year wise) Merchandise Exports were during the year 2011 starting with 19th rank and ending with 2017 20th position.
8. India's rank in world trade (calendar year wise) Merchandise Imports were during the year 2011 starting with 12th rank and ending with 2017 11th position.
9. India's rank in world trade (calendar year wise) Services Exports were during the year 2011 starting with 8th rank and ending with 2017 9th position.
10. India's ranks in world trade (calendar year wise) Services imports were during the year 2011 starting with 9th rank and ending with 2017 10th position.
11. In the year 1949-50 showed that the exports 1,016 (US\$ Million), imports 1,292(US\$ Million) and balance of trade -276 (US\$ Million).
12. During the year 2018-19 reveals that the exports 3,29,536 (US \$ million), imports 5,14,034 (US \$ million) and trade balance -1,84,498 (US \$ million).
13. India's export profile of state-wise share during the year 2018-19 first rank secured by the Maharashtra (22.10%), followed by Gujarat (20.45%) and third position secured by Tamil Nadu (9.26%).
14. Exports share of India by destinations wise during the 2016-17 to 2018-19 revealed that the first position secured by USA, followed by United Arab Emirates and third rank secured by China.
15. Imports share of India by destinations wise during the 2016-17 to 2018-19 revealed that the first position secured by China, followed by USA and third rank secured by United Arab Emirates.
16. Top 10 destinations share of total export of India in world secured by during the years 2016-17 (50.83%), 2017-18 (50.78%) and 2018-19 (50.78%).
17. Top 10 destinations share of total export of India in world secured by during the years 2016-17 (50.82%), 2017-18 (50.32%) and 2018-19 (52.86%).

4. Conclusion

This present research study finally concluded that export profile of India state-wise share were secured by first rank secured by the Maharashtra, followed by Gujarat and third position secured by Tamil Nadu. India's exports by destination revealed that the first position secured by USA, followed by United Arab Emirates and third rank secured by China. India's imports by destination revealed that the first position secured by China, followed by USA and third rank secured by United Arab Emirates. Top ten destinations to

India's total exports were secured by during the years 2016-17 (50.83%), 2017-18 (50.78%) and 2018-19 (50.78%). Top ten destinations to India's total imports were secured by during the years 2016-17 (50.82%), 2017-18 (50.32%) and 2018-19 (52.86%).

This current research study finally suggested that the ministry of commerce and trade, DGCI&S, DGFT, World Trade Organization (WTO), Reserve bank of India and Ministry of finance has to plan implement various new foreign trade policies in all sectors for growth of exports and imports. This will give multipliers effects in employment creation, income generation, foreign exchange earnings and strengthening balance of payment positions. In order to achieve this government of India, various state governments and export promotion councils to provides various monetary and non monetary aids to those who are participants of international trade. It will be golden opportunity for strengthening positive trade balance position of India in future.

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Annex

Table 2 a. India's Export, Imports and trade Balance 1949-50 to 2018-19 (Rs. Crores current)					
Year	Exports (including re-exports)	Imports	Trade Balance	Rate of Change	
				Export (%)	Import (%)
(1)	(2)	(3)	(3)	(4)	(5)
1949-50	485	617	-132	-	-
1950-51	606	608	-2	24.9	-1.5
1951-52	716	890	-174	18.2	46.4
1952-53	578	702	-124	-19.3	-21.1
1953-54	531	610	-79	-8.1	-13.1
1954-55	593	700	-107	11.7	14.8
1955-56	609	774	-165	2.7	10.6
1956-57	605	841	-236	-0.7	8.7
1957-58	561	1035	-474	-7.3	23.1
1958-59	581	906	-325	3.6	-12.5
1959-60	640	961	-321	10.2	6.1
1960-61	642	1122	-480	0.3	16.8
1961-62	660	1090	-430	2.8	-2.9
1962-63	685	1131	-446	3.8	3.8
1963-64	793	1223	-430	15.8	8.1
1964-65	816	1349	-533	2.9	10.3
1965-66	810	1409	-599	-0.7	4.4
1966-67	1157	2078	-921	42.8	47.5
1967-68	1199	2008	-809	3.6	-3.4
1968-69	1358	1909	-551	13.3	-4.9
1969-70	1413	1582	-169	4.1	-17.1
1970-71	1535	1634	-99	8.6	3.3
1971-72	1608	1825	-217	4.8	11.7
1972-73	1971	1867	104	22.6	2.3
1973-74	2523	2955	-432	28	58.3
1974-75	3329	4519	-1190	31.9	52.9
1975-76	4036	5265	-1229	21.2	16.5
1976-77	5142	5074	68	27.4	-3.6
1977-78	5408	6020	-612	5.2	18.6
1978-79	5726	6811	-1085	5.9	13.1
1979-80	6418	9143	-2725	12.1	34.2
1980-81	6711	12549	-5858	4.6	37.3
1981-82	7806	13608	-5802	16.3	8.4
1982-83	8803	14293	-5490	12.8	5
1983-84	9771	15831	-6060	11	10.8
1984-85	11744	17134	-5390	20.2	8.2
1985-86	10895	19658	-8763	-7.2	14.7
1986-87	12452	20096	-7644	14.3	2.2
1987-88	15674	22244	-6570	25.9	10.7
1988-89	20232	28235	-8003	29.1	26.9
1989-90	27658	35328	-7670	36.7	25.1

Source: DGCIS, Kolkata, www.indiabudget.gov.in/economicsurvey/, Economic survey 2018-19, Statistical Appendix

Table 2 b. India's Export, Imports and trade Balance 1949-50 to 2018-19 (Rs. Crores current)

Year	Exports (including re-exports)	Imports	Trade Balance	Rate of Change	
				Export (%)	Import (%)
(1)	(2)	(3)	(3)	(4)	(5)
1990-91	32553	43198	-10645	17.7	22.3
1991-92	44041	47581	-3810	35.3	10.8
1992-93	53688	63375	-9687	21.9	32.4
1993-94	69751	73101	-3350	29.9	15.3
1994-95	82674	89971	-7297	18.5	23.1
1995-96	106353	122678	-16325	28.6	36.4
1996-97	118817	138332	-20103	11.7	13.2
1997-98	130100	215529	-24076	9.5	11
1998-99	139752	228307	-38580	7.4	15.7
1999-00	159095	245200	-56434	13.8	20.9
2000-01	201356	228307	-26950	26.6	5.9
2001-02	209018	245200	-36182	3.8	7.4
2002-03	255137	297206	-42069	22.1	21.2
2003-04	293367	359108	-65741	15	20.8
2004-05	375340	501065	-125725	27.9	39.5
2005-06	456418	660409	-203991	21.6	31.8
2006-07	571779	840506	-268727	25.3	27.3
2007-08	655864	1012312	-356448	14.7	20.4
2008-09	840755	1374436	-533681	28.2	35.8
2009-10	845534	1363736	-518202	0.6	-0.8
2010-11	1142922	1683467	-540545	35.2	23.4
2011-12	1465959	2345463	-879504	28.3	39.3
2012-13	1634319	2669162	-1034843	11.5	13.8
2013-14	1905011	2715434	-810423	16.6	1.7
2014-15	1896348	2737087	-840738	-0.5	0.8
2015-16	1716384	2490306	-773921	-9.5	-9
2016-17	1849434	2577675	-728242	7.8	3.5
2017-18	1956515	3001033	-1044519	5.8	16.4
2018-19*	2307663	3594373	-1286710	18	19.8

Source: DGCI&S, Kolkata, www.indiabudget.gov.in/economicsurvey/, Economic survey 2018-19, Statistical Appendix (Contd.....)

Table 3. Export, Imports and trade balance of India 1949-50 to 2018-19

Year	Exports (incl re-exports) (US\$ Millions)	Imports (US\$ Millions)	Trade Balance (US\$ Millions)	Rate of Change	
				Export (%)	Import (%)
(1)	(2)	(3)	(3)	(4)	(5)
1949-50	1016	1292	-276	-	-
1950-51	1269	1273	-4	24.9	-1.5
1951-52	1490	1852	-362	17.4	45.5
1952-53	1212	1472	-260	-18.7	-20.5
1953-54	1114	1279	-165	-8.1	-13.1
1954-55	1233	1456	-223	10.7	13.8
1955-56	1275	1620	-345	3.4	11.3
1956-57	1259	1750	-491	-1.3	8
1957-58	1171	2160	-989	-7	23.4
1958-59	1219	1901	-682	4.1	-12
1959-60	1343	2016	-673	10.2	6
1960-61	1346	2353	-1007	0.2	16.7
1961-62	1381	2281	-900	2.6	-3.1
1962-63	1437	2372	-935	4.1	4
1963-64	1659	2558	-899	15.4	7.8
1964-65	1701	2813	-1112	2.5	10
1965-66	1693	2944	-1251	-0.5	4.7
1966-67	1628	2923	-1295	-3.8	-0.7
1967-68	1586	2656	-1070	-2.6	-9.1
1968-69	1788	2513	-725	12.7	-5.4
1969-70	1866	2089	-223	4.4	-16.9
1970-71	2031	2162	-131	8.8	3.5
1971-72	2153	2443	-290	6	13
1972-73	2550	2415	135	18.4	-1.1
1973-74	3209	3759	-550	25.8	55.7
1974-75	4174	5666	-1492	30.1	50.7
1975-76	4665	6084	-1419	11.8	7.4
1976-77	5753	5677	76	23.3	-6.7
1977-78	6316	7031	-715	9.8	23.9
1978-79	6978	8300	-1322	10.5	18
1979-80	7947	11321	-3374	13.9	36.4
1980-81	8486	15869	-7383	6.8	40.2
1981-82	8704	15174	-6470	2.6	-4.4
1982-83	9107	14787	-5680	4.6	-2.6
1983-84	9449	15311	-5862	3.8	3.5
1984-85	9878	14412	-4534	4.5	-5.9
1985-86	8904	16067	-7163	-9.9	11.5
1986-87	9745	15727	-5982	9.4	-2.9
1987-88	12089	17156	-5067	24.1	9.1
1988-89	13970	19497	-5527	15.6	13.6
1989-90	16612	21219	-4607	18.9	8.8

Source: DGCI&S, Kolkata, www.indiabudget.gov.in/economicsurvey/, Economic survey 2018-19, Statistical Appendix (Contd.....)

Table 3. Export, Imports and trade balance of India 1949-50 to 2018-19

Year	Exports (incl re-exports) (US\$ Millions)	Imports (US\$ Millions)	Trade Balance (US\$ Millions)	Rate of Change	
				Export (%)	Import (%)
(1)	(2)	(3)	(3)	(4)	(5)
1990-91	18143	24075	-5932	9.2	13.5
1991-92	17865	19411	-1546	-1.5	-19.4
1992-93	18537	21882	-3345	3.8	12.7
1993-94	22238	23306	-1068	20	6.5
1994-95	26330	28654	-2324	18.4	22.9
1995-96	31797	36678	-4881	20.8	28
1996-97	33470	39133	-5663	5.3	6.7
1997-98	35006	41484	-6478	4.6	6
1998-99	33218	42389	-9171	-5.1	2.2
1999-00	36715	49738	-13023	10.5	17.3
2000-01	44076	49975	-5899	20	0.5
2001-02	43827	51413	-7587	-0.6	2.9
2002-03	52719	61412	-8693	20.3	19.4
2003-04	63843	78149	-14307	21.1	27.3
2004-05	83536	111517	-27981	30.8	42.7
2005-06	103091	149166	-46075	23.4	33.8
2006-07	126414	185735	-59321	22.6	24.5
2007-08	163132	251654	-88522	29	35.5
2008-09	185295	303696	-118401	13.6	20.7
2009-10	178751	288373	-109621	-3.5	-5
2010-11	251136	369769	-118633	40.5	28.2
2011-12	305964	489319	-183356	21.8	32.3
2012-13	300401	490737	-190336	-1.8	0.3
2013-14	314405	450200	-135794	4.7	-8.3
2014-15	310338	448033	-137695	-1.3	-0.5
2015-16	262291	381008	-118717	-15.5	-15
2016-17	275852	384357	-108505	5.2	0.9
2017-18	303526	465581	-162055	10	21.1
2018-19*	329536	514034	-184498	8.8	10.4

Source: DGCI&S, Kolkata www.indiabudget.gov.in/economicsurvey/, Economic Survey 2018-19, Statistical Appendix *Provisional

Table 4. Principal Exports (Rs. in Crore)										
		196 0-61	197 0-71	198 0-81	1990 -91	2000- 01	2010- 11	2016- 17	2017- 18	2018- 19
1	Agricultural & allied products:	284	487	2057	6317	28582	111393	226775	249182	271358
1.1	Coffee	7	25	214	252	1185	3010	5646	6245	5722
1.2	Tea and Mate	124	148	426	1070	1976	3354	4906	5397	5828
1.3	Oil cakes	14	55	125	609	2045	11070	5410	7043	10577
1.4	Tobacco	16	33	141	263	871	3985	4250	3828	3984
1.5	Cashew kernels	19	57	140	447	1883	2853	5323	5978	4606
1.6	Spices	17	39	11	239	1619	8043	19111	20085	23218
1.7	Sugar and molasses	30	29	40	38	511	5633	8974	5323	10106
1.8	Raw cotton	12	14	165	846	224	13160	10907	12200	14628
1.9	Rice	0	5	224	462	2943	11586	38443	50308	53990
1.10	Fish and fish preparations	5	31	217	960	6367	11917	39594	47646	47663
1.11	Meat and meat preparations	1	3	56	140	1470	8960	27036	26896	25987
1.12	Fruits, vegetables and pluses	6	12	80	216	1609	6350	12043	11681	12999
1.13	Miscellaneous processed foods	1	4	36	213	1094	3669	5687	5992	6537
2	Ores and minerals (Excl. coal)	52	164	414	1497	4139	39098	33018	36381	41446
2.1	Mica		16	18	35	64	189	374	525	498
2.2	Iron ore (million tone)	17	117	303	1049	1634	21416	10291	9488	9265
3	Manufactured goods	291	772	3747	23736	160723	789433	1362095	1393418	1621779
3.1	Textile fabrics & manufactures	73	145	933	6832			150126	175086	192746
3.1.1	Cotton, yarn & fabrics	65	145	408	2100	16030	13160	57358	57422	68786
3.1.2	Readymade garments	1	29	550	4012	25478	52861	116459	107644	112701
3.2	Coir yarn	6	13	17	48	221	726	1977	2100	2288

3.3	Jute incl twist and yarn	135	190	330	298	932	2092	2080	2159	2274
3.4	Leather goods	28	80	390	2600	8914	17818	34651	34084	35934
3.5	Handicrafts	11	73	952	6167	5097	5877	22909	20969	23227
3.5. 1	Gems and jewellery	1	45	618	5247	33734	18442 0	29090 3	26783 3	28140 8
3.6	Chemicals & allied	7	29	225	2111	22851	13154 4	16705 4	19854 0	26471 8
3.7	Machinery, Transport & Metal	22	198	827	3872	31870	22680 5	47410 6	54853 6	64500 0
4	Minerals fuels and lubricants	7	13	28	948	8822	19263 9	21734 0	24770 2	33514 8
	Total Exports	642	153 5	671 1	3255 3	20135 6	11369 64	18494 34	19565 15	23076 63

Source: (DGCI&S), Kolkata www.indiabudget.gov.in/economicsurvey/, Economic Survey 2018-19, Statistical Appendix *Provisional

		1960 -61	1970 -71	1980 -81	1990 -91	2000 -01	2010- 11	2016- 17	2017- 18	2018- 19*
1	Agricultural & allied products:	596	644	2601	3521	6256	24448	33816	38654	38829
1.1	Coffee	15	33	271	141	259	662	843	969	822
1.2	Tea and Mate	260	196	538	596	433	736	731	837	831
1.3	Oil cakes	29	73	158	339	448	2438	805	1093	1512
1.4	Tobacco	34	43	178	147	191	875	634	594	570
1.5	Cashew kernels	40	76	177	249	412	627	793	927	658
1.6	Spices	36	51	14	133	354	1768	2852	3115	3323
1.7	Sugar and molasses	60	39	50	21	112	1246	1338	826	1444
1.8	Raw cotton	25	19	209	471	49	2910	1621	1894	2104
1.9	Rice	-	7	283	257	644	2545	5734	7806	7753
1.10	Fish	10	40	274	535	1394	2623	5903	7389	6802
1.11	Meat	2	4	70	78	322	1971	4034	4171	3716
1.12	Fruits, vegetables and pluses	13	16	101	120	352	1397	1797	1811	1864
1.13	Miscellane ous	2	6	45	119	239	806	848	930	934
2	Ores and minerals (Excl. coal)	109	217	523	834	906	8581	4924	5644	5927

2.1	Mica		21	22	19	14	42	56	81	71
2.2	Iron ore (million tone)	36	155	384	585	358	4715	1534	1471	1318
3	Manufactured goods	610	1021	4738	13229	35181	173263	203140	216122	231953
3.1	Textile fabrics & manufactures	153	192	1179	3807			22384	27169	27592
3.1.1	Cotton, yarn & fabrics	136	188	516	1170	3509	2910	8550	8908	984
3.1.2	Readymade garments	2	39	696	2236	5577	11614	17368	16707	16138
3.2	Coir yarn	13	17	22	27	48	159	295	326	327
3.3	Jute incl twist and yarn	283	252	417	166	204	459	310	335	325
3.4	Leather goods	59	106	493	1449	1951	3909	5166	5289	5141
3.5	Handicrafts	23	96	1204	3437	1116	1293	3417	3253	3320
3.5.1	Gems and jewellery	2	59	782	2924	7384	40509	43413	41544	40251
3.6	Chemicals & allied	15	39	284	1176	5002	28905	24911	30800	37840
3.7	Machinery, Transport & Metal	46	261	1045	2158	6976	49815	70723	85089	92451
4	Minerals fuels and lubricants	15	17	35	528	1931	42280	324415	38438	47874
	Total Exports	1346	2031	8486	18143	44076	251136	2758512	303526	330070
Source: DGCI&S, Kolkata, www.indiabudget.gov.in/economicsurvey/ , Economic Survey 2018-19, Statistical Appendix *Provisional. Note: 1.13: Miscellaneous processed foods										

Table 6. Principal Imports (Rs. in Crore)										
		1960 -61	1970 -71	1980 -81	1990 -91	2000- 01	2010- 11	2016- 17	2017- 18	2018- 19
1	Food & Live animals for foods	214	242	380	-	-	-	-	-	-
1.1	Cereals & cereals preparations	181	213	100	182	90	545	9589	3464	1476
2	Raw materials & intermediate	527	889	9760	-	-	-	-	-	-
2.1	cashew nuts(unprocessed)	-	29	9	134	962	2650	9027	9134	11162
2.2	Cure rubber	11	4	32	226	695	8074	10030	12034	14207
2.3	Fibres	101	127	164	-	-	-	-	-	-
2.3.1	Synthetic & regenerated fibres	-	9	97	56	275	957	2454	2378	3275
2.3.2	Raw wool	1	15	43	182	458	1435	1894	1885	2160
2.3.3	Raw cotton	82	99	-	1	1185	624	6339	6307	4383
2.3.4	Raw jute	8	-	1	20	84	302	704	289	236
2.4	Petroleum, oil & lubricants	69	136	5264	10816	71497	482282	583217	700321	986260
2.5	Animal vegetable oils & fats	5	39	709	-	-	-	-	-	-
2.5.1	Edible oils	4	23	677	326	6093	29860	73039	74996	69024
2.6	Fertilizers & chemical products	88	217	1490	-	-	-	-	-	-
2.6.1	Fertilizers & Fertilizers mfr	13	86	818	1766	3034	31533	33706	34654	52095
2.6.2	Chemical elements & compounds	39	68	358	2289	1542	13278	147356	175944	220476
2.6.3	Dyeing & colouring materials	1	9	21	168	874	5368	15307	18610	22538
2.6.4	Medical & pharmaceutical	10	24	85	468	1723	11114	33502	35330	44429
2.6.5	Plastic materials	9	8	121	1095	2551	31304	80227	93384	109629
2.7	Pulp & waste paper	7	12	18	458	1290	5208	6537	7442	9186
2.8	Paper & paper board	12	25	187	456	2005	9614	17456	21285	24886
2.9	Non-metallic minerals	6	33	555	-	797	-	-	-	-

2.9.1	Pearls, precious stones	1	25	417	3738	22101	157596	159464	220966	188881
2.10	Iron & steel	123	147	852	2113	3569	47275	55278	67235	87984
2.11	Non-ferrous metals	47	119	477	1102	2462	212153	262961	320381	358671
3	Capital Goods	356	404	1910	10466	25821	231712	378724	407051	497160
1	Manufacture of metals	23	9	90	302	1786	15167	28028	35022	42460
2	Non-electrical machinery	203	258	1089	4240	16915	118928	100318	110681	137630
3	Electrical machinery	57	70	260	1702	2227	17510	84126	101447	126931
4	Transport equipment	72	67	472	1670	4353	52112	152337	146509	173521
	Total Imports	1122	1634	12549	43198	228307	1683467	2577675	3001033	3594373

Source: (DGCI&S), Kolkata www.indiabudget.gov.in/economicsurvey/, Economic Survey 2018-19, Statistical Appendix *Provisional

		1960-61	1970-71	1980-81	1990-91	2000-01	2010-11	2016-17	2017-18	2018-19
1	Food& Live animals for foods	449	321	481	-	-	-	-	-	-
1.1	Cereals & cereals preparations	380	282	127	102	20	119	1429	536	211
2	Raw materials & intermediate	1105	1176	12341	-	-	-	-	-	-
2.1	cashew nuts(unprocessed)	-	39	11	75	211	578	1347	1419	1608
2.2	Cure rubber	23	5	40	126	152	1771	1496	1867	2002
2.3	Fibres	212	168	208	-	-	-	-	-	-
2.3.1	Synthetic & regenerated fibres	-	12	122	31	60	210	366	369	467
2.3.2	Raw wool	2	20	55	102	100	315	282	292	310
2.3.3	Raw cotton	172	131	-	0	259	137	947	979	633
2.3.4	Raw jute	17	0	1	11	18	67	105	45	34
2.4	Petroleum, oil& lubricants	145	180	6656	6028	15650	105964	86964	108659	140918
2.5	Animal vegetable oils & fats	10	51	896	-	-	-	-	-	-
2.5.1	Edible oils	8	31	857	182	1334	6551	10893	11637	9890

2.6	Fertilizers & chemical products	185	286	1884	-	-	-	-	-	-
2.6.1	Fertilizers & Fertilizers mfr	27	113	1034	984	664	6885	5024	5376	7467
2.6.2	Chemical elements & compounds	82	90	453	1276	338	2914	21974	27295	31535
2.6.3	Dyeing & colouring materials	2	12	26	94	191	1178	2283	2888	3222
2.6.4	Medical & pharmaceutical	21	32	107	261	377	2436	4995	5481	6359
2.6.5	Plastic materials	19	11	154	610	558	6874	11964	14488	15681
2.7	Pulp & waste paper	15	16	23	255	282	1145	975	1155	1312
2.8	Paper & paper board	25	33	236	254	439	2111	2602	3303	3559
2.9	Non-metallic minerals	13	44	702	-	174	-	-	-	-
2.9.1	Pearls, precious stones	2	33	527	2083	4838	34620	23809	34279	27076
2.10	Iron & steel	258	194	1078	1178	781	10376	8239	10432	12582
2.11	Non-ferrous metals	99	158	604	614	539	46677	39226	49683	51379
3	Capital Goods	747	534	2416	5833	5534	50907	56437	63154	71054
1	Manufacture of metals	48	12	113	168	391	3332	4178	5435	6065
2	Non-electrical machinery	426	341	1377	2363	3703	26111	14954	17176	19671
3	Electrical machinery	120	93	328	949	487	3845	12543	15732	18182
4	Transport equipment	151	88	597	931	953	11467	22688	22733	24760
	Total Imports	2353	2162	15869	24075	51413	369769	384357	465581	514034
Source: (DGCI&S), Kolkata www.indiabudget.gov.in/economicsurvey/ , Economic Survey 2018-19, Statistical Appendix *Provisional										

2.8 India's Export profile: State-wise share 2016-17 to 2018-19

Table 12 shows that the India's export profile of state-wise share 2016-17 first rank secured by the Maharashtra 67433.77(US \$ million) (24.45%), followed by Gujarat 54213.62(US \$ million) (19.65%) and third position secured by Tamil Nadu 26452.98(US \$ million) (9.59%).

In the year 2017-18 first rank secured by the Maharashtra 69731.48 (US \$ million) (22.99%), followed by Gujarat 66818.03 (US \$ million) (22.02%) and third position secured by Tamil Nadu 29754.22 (US \$ million) (9.81%).

During the year 2018-19 first rank secured by the Maharashtra 72814.49 (US \$ million) (22.10%), followed by Gujarat 67401.18 (US \$ million) (20.45%) and third position secured by Tamil Nadu 30524.25 (US \$ million) (9.26%) and remaining place secured by rest of the states of India.

S No	States/UT	2016-17	% Share	2017-18	% Share	2018-19	% share	% Change	% Change
1	Maharashtra	67434	24.45	69731.48	22.99	72814.49	22.10	3.41	4.42
2	Gujarat	54214	19.65	66818.03	22.02	67401.18	20.45	23.25	0.87
3	Tamil Nadu	26453	9.59	29754.22	9.81	30524.25	9.26	12.48	2.59
4	Unspecified	11595	4.20	8685.29	2.86	20891.68	6.34	-25.10	140.54
5	Karnataka	19685	7.14	18052.34	5.95	17351.26	5.27	-8.29	-3.88
6	Uttar Pradesh	12529	4.54	13803.90	4.55	16291.23	4.94	10.18	18.02
7	Haryana	11940	4.33	13019.53	4.29	14082.96	4.27	24.02	6.18
8	Andhra Pradesh	1069	3.88	13263.41	4.37	13832.88	4.20	9.04	6.25
9	West Bengal	8236	2.99	9148.22	3.02	9921.28	3.01	11.07	8.45
10	Kerala	4886	1.77	7308.07	2.41	9767.46	2.96	49.57	33.65
11	Delhi	10554	3.83	8713.88	2.87	9467.51	2.87	-17.44	8.65
12	Telangana	6001	2.18	6568.71	2.17	7228.47	2.19	9.46	10.04
13	Rajasthan	5772	2.09	6952.05	2.29	7061.61	2.14	20.44	1.58
14	Madhya Pradesh	4437	1.61	5249.96	1.73	6382.37	1.94	18.33	21.57
15	Orissa	6071	2.20	7585.01	2.50	6303.15	1.91	24.95	-16.90
16	Punjab	5277	1.91	5788.25	1.91	6038.07	1.83	9.70	4.32
17	Uttaranchal	897	0.33	1455.46	0.48	2351.18	0.71	62.70	61.54
18	Dadra & Haveli	1563	0.57	2051.25	0.68	2143.38	0.65	31.25	4.49
19	Goa	2281	0.83	2103.17	0.69	2063.78	0.63	-7.81	-1.87
20	Bihar	824	0.30	1345.31	0.44	1640.33	0.50	63.36	21.93
21	Himachal Pradesh	1051	0.38	1221.67	0.40	1323.43	0.40	15.69	8.33
22	Chhattisgarh	717	0.26	1116.53	0.37	1252.65	0.38	61.50	-17.73
23	Jharkhand	943	0.34	1522.70	0.50	1243.44	0.38	55.69	11.37
24	Daman and Diu	728	0.26	956.98	0.32	1053.39	0.32	31.49	10.07
25	Pondicherry	310	0.11	415.05	0.14	392.79	0.12	33.65	-5.36
26	Assam	430	0.16	382.35	0.13	369.76	0.11	-11.09	-3.29
27	Jammu & Kashmir	118	0.04	148.31	0.05	196.43	0.06	25.89	32.45
28	Chandigarh	89.3	0.03	69.93	0.02	71.89	0.02	-21.73	2.81
29	Meghalaya	102	0.04	85.13	0.03	51.09	0.02	-16.65	-39.98
30	Sikkim	4.91	0.00	13.96	0.00	7.91	0.00	184.36	-43.33
31	A& N Islands	2.33	0.00	31.46	0.01	4.01	0.00	1247.74	-87.26
32	Manipur	0.74	0.00	3.92	0.00	2.78	0.00	25.82	108.84
33	Nagaland	1.06	0.00	1.33	0.00	2.66	0.00	432.13	-32.12
34	Arunachal Pradesh	4.93	0.00	5.32	0.00	2.23	0.00	7.92	-58.06
35	Tripura	1.42	0.00	2.36	0.00	1.43	0.00	66	39.40
36	Mizoram	0.03	0.00	1.07	0.00	1.33	0.00	3638.24	24.16
	Lakshadweep	0.43	0.00	0.64	0.00	0.41	0.00	47.38	-35.90
	Total	275852	100	303376.23	100	329536.16	100	9.98	8.62

Source: Monthly Bulletin on Foreign Trade May 2019

2.9 Inferential Statistical Results and Discussion

1. Hypothesis Testing-1

(1) Null and Alternative Hypothesis

The below 11, 12 & 13 table shows that tested results of Hypothesis.

H0: $\mu_1 = \mu_2$: There is no association with the exports and imports (US\$ Million) in India during years 1949-50 to 2018-19.

H1: $\mu_1 \neq \mu_2$: There is association with exports and imports (US\$ Million) in India during years 1949-50 to 2018-19.

(Pair- I)	N	Mean	SD	Standard Err Mean
VAR1	70	59340.8286	99847.47903	11934.05635
VAR2	70	87350.4000	152183.40055	18189.39542
Source: SPSS Output		VAR1 (Exports US\$ Million) and VAR2 (Imports US\$ Million)		

(2) Significance level: 5%

Pair-1	N	Correlation	Sig.
VAR1&VAR2	70	0.998	0.000
Source: SPSS Output		VAR1 (Exports US\$ Million) and VAR2 (Imports US\$ Million)	

(3) Test statistic: The t- test statistic results shows at : $t=-4.419$

Pair-I	mean	SD	Std error mean	level of significance		t	df	Sig.(2-tailed)
				lower	upper			
VAR1-VAR2	-28009.57	53028.11	6338.07	-40653.68	15365.47	4.419	69	0.000
Source: SPSS Output, VAR1 (Exports US\$ Million) and VAR2 (Imports US\$ Million)								

(4) **Result:** This is showed that the absolute value of $t -4.419 = 4.419 > t_c = 1.955$. The P-value is 0 ($P=0 < 0.05$). It is found that the null hypothesis is not accepted. It is sufficient evidence to declare that the μ_1 is distinct than μ_2 ($\mu_1 \neq \mu_2$), for 0.05 level of significance.

2.Hypothesis Testing-2

(1) Null and Alternative Hypothesis

The below 14, 15 & 16 table shows that tested results of Hypothesis.

H0: $\mu_1 = \mu_2$: There is no association with exports and trade balance (US\$ Million) in India during years 1949-50 to 2018-19.

H1: $\mu_1 \neq \mu_2$: There is association with exports and trade balance (US\$ Million) in India during years 1949-50 to 2018-19.

Table 14 Results of Paired t test				
(Pair – II)	N	Mean	SD	Standard Err Mean
VAR1	70	59340.8286	99847.47903	11934.05635
VAR3	70	-28009.5857	53028.08626	6338.06858
Source: SPSS Output		VAR1 (Exports US\$ Million) and VAR3 (Trade Balance US\$ Million)		

(2) Significance level: 5%

Table 15 Paired t test correlations			
Pair-II	N	Correlation	Sig.
VAR1&VAR3	70	-0.980	0.000
Source: SPSS Output		VAR1 (Exports US\$ Million) and VAR (Trade Balance US\$ Million)	

(3) Test statistic: The t- test statistic results shows at : **t=4.802**

Table 16 Results of Paired t test								
Pair II	mean	SD	Std error mean	level of significance		df	t	Sigf.
				lower	upper			
VAR1- VAR3	87350.41	152183.38	18189.39	51063.57	123637.26	69	4.802	0.000
Source: SPSS Output, VAR1 (Exports US\$ Million) and VAR3 (Trade Balance US\$ Million)								

(4) Result: This is showed that the absolute value of **t = 4.802 > tc = 1.955**. The P-value is 0 ($P=0 < 0.05$). It is found that the null hypothesis is *not accepted*. It is sufficient evidence to declare that the **μ_1 is distinct than μ_2 ($\mu_1 \neq \mu_2$)**, for 0.05 level of significance.

3.Hypothesis Testing-3

(1) Null and Alternative Hypothesis

The below 17, 18 &19 table shows that tested results of Hypothesis.

H0: $\mu_1 = \mu_2$: There is no association with imports and trade balance (US\$ Million) in India during years 1949-50 to 2018-19.

H1: $\mu_1 \neq \mu_2$: There is association with imports and trade balance (US\$ Million) in India during years 1949-50 to 2018-19.

Table 17 Results of Paired t test				
(Pair – III)	N	Mean	SD	Standard Err Mean
VAR2	70	87350.4000	152183.40055	18189.39542
VAR3	70	-28009.5857	53028.08626	6338.06858
Source: SPSS Output		VAR2 (Imports US\$ Million) and VAR3 (Trade Balance US\$ Million)		

(2) Significance level: 5%

Table 18 Paired t test correlations			
Pair-III	N	Correlation	Sig.
VAR2&VAR3	70	-0.991	0.000
Source: SPSS Output		VAR2 (Imports US\$ Million) and VAR3 (Trade Balance US\$ Million)	

(3) Test statistic: The t- test statistic results shows at : $t=4.711$

Table 19 Paired Samples t Test Result								
Pair III	mean	SD	Std error mean	level of significance		df	t	Sigf.
				lower	upper			
VAR2-VAR3	115359.99	204875.59	24487.32	66509.13	164210.85	69	4.711	0.000
Source: SPSS Output, VAR2 (Imports US\$ Million) and VAR3 (Trade Balance US\$ Million)								

(4) **Result:** This is showed that the $t = 4.711 > t_c = 1.955$. The P-value is 0 ($P=0 < 0.05$). It is found that the null hypothesis is *not accepted*. It is sufficient evidence to declare that the μ_1 is *distinct than μ_2* ($\mu_1 \neq \mu_2$), for 0.05 level of significance.

4.Hypothesis Testing-4

(1) Null and Alternative Hypothesis

The below 20, 21 & 22 table shows that tested results of Hypothesis.

H0: $\mu_1 = \mu_2$: There is no association with India’s top 10 exports (US\$ Million) and India’s top 10 imports (US\$ Million) by countries 2016-17.

H1: $\mu_1 \neq \mu_2$: There is association with India’s top 10 exports (US\$ Million) and India’s top 10 imports (US\$ Million) by countries 2016-17.

Table 20 Results of Paired t test				
(Pair –IV)	N	Mean	SD	Standard Err Mean
VAR4	11	25077.4955	38534.46786	11618.57922
VAR7	11	34941.5482	53202.93530	16041.28856
Source: SPSS Output		VAR4 - India’s top 10 exports (US\$ Million) 2016-17 and VAR7- India’s top 10 imports (US\$ Million) 2016-17		

(2) Significance level: 5%

Table 21 Paired t test correlations			
Pair IV	N	Correlation	Sig.
VAR4&VAR7	11	0.990	0.000
Source: SPSS Output		VAR4 - India’s top 10 exports (US\$ Million) 2016-17 and VAR7- India’s top 10 imports (US\$ Million) 2016-17	

(3) Test statistic: The t- test statistic results shows at : **t=-2.042**

Table 22 Paired Samples t Test Result								
Pair IV	mean	SD	Std error mean	level of significance		df	t	Sigf.
				lower	upper			
VAR4-VAR7	-9864.05	16019.99	4830.21	-20626.42	898.32	10	-2.042	0.068
Source: SPSS Output, VAR4 - India’s top 10 exports (US\$ Million) 2016-17 and VAR7- India’s top 10 imports (US\$ Million) 2016-17								

(4) Result: This is showed that the **t = - 2.042 > tc = 2.228**. The P-value is 0.068 (**P=0.068 < 0.05**). It is found that the null hypothesis is *accepted*. It is sufficient evidence to declare that the **μ_1 is non-different than μ_2** , for 0.05 level of significance.

5. Hypothesis Testing-5

(1) Null and Alternative Hypothesis

The below 23, 24 & 25table shows that tested results of Hypothesis.

H0: $\mu_1 = \mu_2$: There is no associationwith India’s top 10 exports (US\$ Million) and India’s top 10 imports (US\$ Million) by countries 2017-18.

H1: $\mu_1 \neq \mu_2$: There is associationwith India’s top 10 exports (US\$ Million) and India’s top 10 imports (US\$ Million) by countries 2017-18.

Table 23 Results of Paired t test				
(Pair –V)	N	Mean	SD	Standard Err Mean
VAR5	11	27593.2855	42256.50230	12740.81483
VAR9	11	42325.5455	65322.83756	19695.57658
Source: SPSS Output		VAR5- India’s top 10 exports (US\$ Million) 2017-18 and VAR9- India’s top 10 imports (US\$ Million) 2017-18		

(2) Significance level: 5%

Table 24 Paired t test correlations			
Pair-V	N	Correlation	Sig.
VAR5&VAR9	11	0.996	0.000
Source: SPSS Output		VAR5- India’s top 10 exports (US\$ Million) 2017-18 and VAR9- India’s top 10 imports (US\$ Million) 2017-18	

(3) Test statistic: The t- test statistic results shows at : **t=-2.072**

Table 25 Paired Samples t Test Result								
Pair V	mean	SD	Std error mean	level of significance		df	t	Sigf.
				lower	upper			
VAR5- VAR9	-14732.26	23579.20	7109.40	-30572.98	1108.46	10	-2.072	0.065
Source: SPSS Output, VAR5- India’s top 10 exports (US\$ Million) 2017-18 and VAR9- India’s top 10 imports (US\$ Million) 2017-18								

(4) Result: This is showed that the **t = - 2.072 > tc = 2.228**. The **P-value** is 0.065 (**P=0.065 < 0.05**). It is found that the null hypothesis is **accepted**. It is sufficient evidence to declare that the **μ_1 is non-different than μ_2** , for 0.05 level of significance.

6. Hypothesis Testing-6

(1) Null and Alternative Hypothesis

The below 26, 27 & 28 table shows that tested results of Hypothesis.

H0: $\mu_1 = \mu_2$: There is no association with India's top 10 exports (US\$ Million) and India's top 10 imports (US\$ Million) by countries 2018-19.

H1: $\mu_1 \neq \mu_2$: There is association with India's top 10 exports (US\$ Million) and India's top 10 imports (US\$ Million) by countries 2018-19.

Table 26 Results of Paired t test				
(Pair – VI)	N	Mean	SD	Standard Err Mean
VAR6	11	165553.1255	447669.87357	134977.54551
VAR10	11	46665.6764	66675.91344	20103.54431
Source: SPSS Output	VAR6- India's top 10 exports (US\$ Million) 2018-19 and VAR10- India's top 10 imports (US\$ Million) 2018-19			

(2) Significance level: 5%

Table 27 Paired t test correlations			
(Pair – VI)	N	Correlation	Sig.
VAR6&VAR10	11	0.029	0.933
Source: SPSS Output	VAR6- India's top 10 exports (US\$ Million) 2018-19 and VAR10- India's top 10 imports (US\$ Million) 2018-19		

(3) Test statistic: The t- test statistic results shows at : **t=0.875**

Table 28 Paired Samples t Test Result								
(Pair VI)	mean	SD	Std error mean	level of significance		df	t	Sigf.
				lower	upper			
VAR6- VAR10	118887.45	450690.93	135888.43	183890.84	421665.74	10	0.875	0.402
Source: SPSS Output, VAR6- India's top 10 exports (US\$ Million) 2018-19 and VAR10- India's top 10 imports (US\$ Million) 2018-19								

(4) **Result:** This is showed that the **t = 0.875 > tc = 2.228**. The P-value is 0.402 (**P=0.402 < 0.05**). It is found that the null hypothesis is **accepted**. It is sufficient evidence to declare that the **μ_1 is non-different than μ_2** , for 0.05 level of significance.

7. Hypothesis Testing-7

(1) Null and Alternative Hypothesis

The below 29, 30 & 31 table shows that tested results of Hypothesis.

H0: $\mu_1 = \mu_2 = \mu_3$: There is no association with exports, imports and trade balance (US\$ Million) in India during years 1949-50 to 2018-19.

H1: $\mu_1 \neq \mu_2 \neq \mu_3$: There is association with exports, imports and trade balance (US\$ Million) in India during years 1949-50 to 2018-19.

Table 29 Model summary				
Model	R	R square	Adj R Square	std. error of the estimate
1	1*	1	1	0.272
Source: Output of SPSS		*Predictors(constant), VAR1 & VAR2		

(2) Significance level: 5%

Table 30 ANOVA F Test					
Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig
Between Groups	194026477348.030	2	97013238674.015	1311574915601.137	0.000
Within groups (Error)	4.956	67	0.74		
Total	194026477352.986	69			
Source: SPSS Output		*Dependent Variable VAR3 **Predictors(constant), VAR1 & VAR2			

(3) Test statistic: The t- test statistic results shows at : F =1311574915601.137

Table 31 Coefficients					
Model	US coefficients		St coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	std error	beta		
	-0.028	0.039		-0.714	0.478
VAR1	1.000	0.000	1.883	211148	0.000
VAR2	-1.000	0.000	-2.870	-321823	0.000
Source: SPSS Output		*Dependent Variable VAR3			

(5) **Result:** The P-value is 0 ($P=0 < 0.05$). It is found that the null hypothesis is *rejected*. It is sufficient evidence to declare that the μ_1, μ_2 is *different than* μ_3 ($\mu_1 \neq \mu_2 \neq \mu_3$), for 0.05 level of significance.

8.Hypothesis Testing-1

(1) Null and Alternative Hypothesis

The below 4, 5 &6 table shows that tested results of Hypothesis.

H0: $\mu_1 = \mu_2$: There is no association with rate of change exports (%) and rate of change imports (%) in India during years 1949-50 to 2018-19.

H1: $\mu_1 \neq \mu_2$: There is association with rate of change exports (%) and rate of change imports (%) in India during years 1949-50 to 2018-19.

(2) **Test statistic:** The t- test results shows at : $t = -0.519$

(3) **Significance level:** 5%

(4) **Result:** This is showed that the $t = 0.519 > t_c = 2.228$. The P-value is 0.556 ($P = 0.556 < 0.05$). It is found that the null hypothesis is *accepted*. It is sufficient evidence to declare that the μ_1 is *non-different than* μ_2 , for 0.05 level of significance.

India's total exports were secured by during the years 2016-17 (50.83%), 2017-18 (50.78%) and 2018-19 (50.78%). Top ten destinations to India's total imports were secured by during the years 2016-17 (50.82%), 2017-18 (50.32%) and 2018-19 (52.86%).

This current research study finally suggested that the ministry of commerce and trade, DGCI&S, DGFT, World Trade Organization (WTO), Reserve bank of India and Ministry of finance has to plan implement various new foreign trade policies in all sectors for growth of exports and imports. This will give multipliers effects in employment creation, income generation, foreign exchange earnings and strengthening balance of payment positions. In order to achieve this government of India, various state governments and export promotion councils to provides various monetary and non monetary aids to those who are participants of international trade. It will be golden opportunity for strengthening positive trade balance position of India in future.

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